

Effects of Citric Acid and Potash on the weight of *Helianthus annuus L.* in Pb and Anthracene Co-contaminated soil

Nwosu O. U^{1*}, Nwawuike N^{1.}, Amanze C. T^{2.}, Osuagwu C. O^{3.}, Ononogbo C^{4.}, Nwoko C. O^{5.}, Ukabiala M. E^{2.}

¹Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State.

²Department of Soil Science, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State.

³Department of Agricultural Economics, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State.

⁴Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State.

⁵Department of Environmental Management, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo State.

*Corresponding author: nwosuoly@gmail.com

Received: March 18, 2024; Accepted: August 10, 2024; Published: August 18, 2024.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13337646>

Abstract: Using organic acid as a boost is effectual in phyoremediation of co-contaminated soil. A field experiment was carried out to dictate the impact of citric acid, potash and citric acid+ potash on weight of *Helianthus annuus L.* in Co-contaminated soil. The experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) and treatments were reproduced three times. The findings show that in co-contamination with Pb and anthracene treated soil, the joint use of potash + citric acid and potash promoted the dry weight of *Helianthus annuus L.* by 3% and 26% respectively relative to control treatments (no contamination and no amendments) while the single use of citric acid reduced the shoot dry matter yield of *Helianthus annuus L.* by 6%. There was a significant difference at the shoot dry weights of plants grown in Pb and Pb-anthracene co-contaminated soil.

Keywords: *Organic acid, Helianthus annuus L, Co-contaminated soil, Potash.*

Introduction

Rapid growth in industrialization has become a very big challenge and a crucial factor for reducing the quality of the environment owing to organic and inorganic pollution (Khalid *et al.*, 2020). Most studies have shown that the integration of these pollutants could have high rise on the biosphere (Chigbo, *et al.*, 2013).

Phytoremediation, also called eco-friendly remediation, green and sustainable remediation that uses plants, soil micro biota and amendments to take off, accommodate or make the heavy metals non-irritant in the soil (Nwosu, 2023). This technology is good at removing organic and inorganic pollutants. There is a raising need to research on phytoremediation of co-

contaminated soil (Chigbo, *et al.*, 2013; Hechmi *et al.*, 2013). Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*), of the asteraceae family is of high interest in phytoextraction because it can be grown under stress such as heavy metal stress (Piracha *et al.* 2019; Niu *et al.*, 2023). This plant can amass enormous amount of contaminants on its roots and translocate them to shoot compartment of the plants. It also produces enormous amount of biomass (Blaylock *et al.*, 1997; Farid *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, the successfulness of phytoremediation partly depends on the dissolving ability and readiness of the metal in soil to be taken up by the roots. Mostly, heavy metals integrated in soil particles are difficult to be taken up by plants (Han *et al.*, 2018; Niu *et al.*, 2023). Lately, some chemical amendments are found useful in advancing phytoremediation procedure but chemical amendments have adverse effect on soil microorganisms which also affect plant growth (Niu *et al.*, 2023). In other to boost phytoextraction, an alternative method to chemical amendment have been carried out. This is the use of low molecular mass organic acids (LMMOAs). This applied method has global attention in phytoremediation (Afshan *et al.*, 2015; Guo *et al.*, 2019). The chelate-enhancing capacity of LMMOAs has been extensively recorded in studies concerning *Helianthus annuus L.*, *Brassica napus L.* and *Brassica juncea L.* under different heavy metal stress

(Sallah-Ud-Din *et al.*, 2017). LMMOAs, such as citric acid (CA) and oxalic acid, found in root exudates, have the ability to regulate redox coupling processes, facilitate anion-cation exchange, and influence soil respiration (Niu *et al.*, 2023). Research conducted by Najeeb *et al.* (2011) indicated that LMMOAs have the potential to enhance plant growth by altering the speciation of elements, promoting the bioavailability of heavy metals and consequently, significantly modifying the uptake of essential ions by plants. Potash is carbonaceous in nature and the potash used for this project was produced from empty palm fruit bunch. It has many potential benefits on soil properties such as increase in soil biological activities, increase in pH and nutrient uptake. It also possesses anions like phosphate, chloride, nitrate and sulphate which act as a degrading agent (Udoetok, 2012; Ogbuehi, 2016). Despite the effectiveness of LMMOAs as innovative agents in mitigating the adverse effects of heavy metals and enhancing phytoremediation efforts, there is a scarcity of literature on the utilization of citric acid and potash as amendments in the remediation of co-contaminated soil by *Helianthus annuus L.* as noted by Ash *et al.* (2016). This study will principally focus on effect of potash, citric acid and citric acid + potash concerning growth effect of

Helianthus annuus L. in Co-contaminated soil.

Materials and Methods

Dry seeds of *Helianthus annuus L.* were obtained from National Seeds Service, Umudike. Lead, antracene and cirtic acid was acquired from Finlab, Nigeria. Soils (0-20cm) depth with moisture content 1.29%, CEC 640 Cmol/kg, pH 4.8., organic matter 1.97%, total nitrogen content 0.1 5%, silt 3.45%, sand 91%, and clay 5.15% (sandy loam) were used in a farm land in Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo state which lies within latitudes 5°23' 35.0'North and longitude 6°59'05.0'' East at height above sea level of 55m. The environment is tropical humid with average temperature of 29°C.

Experimental design of field trial

An experimental plot measuring 10 meters by 9 meters (90 square meters) was designated for the study. The area was cleared of existing grasses through slashing and removal. The plots were tilled using minimum tillage method. The study was organized using a randomized complete block design (RCBD), with treatments replicated three times. Pre-planting and post-planting, plant and soil analysis was carried out. The plot was divided into 42 experimental blocks. Each block is measured 1m x 1m and was separated from each other by 50cm alley.

Experimental design for assessment of the effect of citric acid and potash in the remediation of co-contaminated soil using Helianthu sannuus L.(Field Exp.)

The experiment was organized in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) of 9 treatments replicated three times.

Table 1 Experimental layout for assessment of the effect of citric acid and potash in the remediation of co-contaminated soil using *Helianthus annuus L.*

Treatments	Codes
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> + 300mg/kg	Pb+CiHPbc
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> + 300mg/kg	Pb+PHPbp
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> + 300mg/kg	Pb+Ci+PHPbc+p
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> + 300mg/kg	Pb +PAH+CiHPbPAHc
Soil+ <i>H.annuus</i> +300mg/kg	Pb+PAH+PHPbPAHp
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> + 300mg/kg	Pb +PAH+Ci+PHPbPAHc+p
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> +PAH+CiHPAHc	
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> +PAH+PHPAHp	
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> +PAH+Ci+PHPAHc+p	
Control	
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> + 300mg/kg	Pb
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> + 300mg/kg	Pb +PAH
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i> +PAH	
Soil + <i>H.annuus</i>	
Soil + PAH	

Soil preparation and Planting

Beds were constructed using a shovel to a height of 30 cm. Seeds of *Helianthus annuus L.* were sown at a depth of 5 cm, with two seeds per hole and a spacing of 50 cm between rows and within rows. The plants were thinned to one after germination. The treatments were replicated 3 times making a total of 42 blocks. Any lost stands were promptly replaced, and weeding was consistently conducted throughout the experiment, typically using a hand hoe at intervals of three weeks. The planting distance gave 9 plants per block. The raised beds in the field locations were encircled by

a 1-meter tall chicken wire barrier to deter rabbits, birds and other wildlife from entering.

The additives applied included citric acid, potash, and a combined mixture of citric acid and potash. Citric acid and potash were introduced into the blocks; 5 weeks after planting respectively. The entire set of amendments were divided into three equal portions and administered weekly over a span of three weeks. Among the treatments was the control soil, which received no application of any amendment. 12 g of citric acid, 90 g of potash and 12 g citric acid + 90 g of potash were administered as solutions

to each soil surface at proportion of 6 g and 30 g for citric acid and potash consecutively for three weeks to dismiss the impact of the amendments on plant growth.

After 70 days of planting, three plant samples were randomly sampled by uprooting them. The plants selected for sampling underwent a rigorous washing process with tap water followed by two rinses with deionized water. Subsequently, the sampled plants were separated into root and shoot components. The samples were oven dried to ascertain their dry mass at 75 °C for 45 h. The dried samples were weighed using analytical balance to determine dry weight.

Statistical Analysis

All gathered data underwent statistical analysis employing the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 21) software package) by SPSS Inc. Treatment effects were assessed through analysis of variance (ANOVA). In instances where a significant variance among treatments was detected, Tukey's HSD test was conducted for multiple comparisons. Significance was determined at a p-value of ≤ 0.05 .

Results and Discussion

Citric acid, potash and citric acid+potash effect on growth of Helianthus annuus L.

Helianthus annuus L. planted in Pb polluted soil showed normal development and no visual symptoms of toxicity to Pb. Sunflowers (*Helianthus annuus L.*) grown in lead-contaminated soil exhibited regular growth and displayed no visible signs of lead toxicity, in contrast to the treatments without any amendments. In contrast to the untreated control, the incorporation of citric acid and citric acid + potash led to a notable decrease in shoot dry matter yield, with reductions of 6% and 3%, respectively, while the addition of potash significantly enhanced the shoot dry matter yield of *Helianthus annuus L.* by 24%. (Figure 1).

The presence of anthracene alone in the soil influenced the growth of *Helianthus annuus L.*, and this impact was altered by the introduction of amendments. Citric acid resulted in a 5% reduction in shoot dry matter, whereas the inclusion of potash or a combination of potash and citric acid significantly boosted plant shoot dry matter by 11% and 2%, respectively.

In co-contamination with Pb and anthracene treated soil, the joint application of potash + citric acid and potash promoted the growth of *Helianthus annuus L.* by 3% and 26% respectively relative to control treatments (no contamination and no amendments)

while the single application of citric acid reduced the shoot dry matter yield of *Helianthus annuus L.* by 6%.

A notable contrast was observed in the shoot dry weights of plants cultivated in soil

contaminated solely with lead compared to those grown in soil contaminated with both lead and anthracene.

Figure 1 Plant shoot dry matter yield was evaluated in the field to assess the impact of citric acid, potash, and their combination in remediating co-contaminated soil using *H. annuus*. Significant differences were identified using Tukey's HSD test ($p \leq 0.05$), with different letters denoting distinct treatments: c for citric acid, p for potash, and c/p for citric acid + potash.

Figure 2 Plant root dry matter yield as affected by citric acid, potash and citric acid+potash in the remediation of co-contaminated soil using *H.annuus* in field. Different letters indicate significant difference (TukeyHSD, $p \leq 0.05$). c=citric acid, p=potash, c/p=citric acid+potash.

Table 2 Anthracene dissipation in field trial in planted and non-planted soil as affected by citric acid, potash and citric acid+potash.

Treatments	Anthracene dissipation (%)
Soil +PAH	30±1.73a
Soil +PAH+ <i>H.annuus</i>	37±1.73ab
Soil +PAH+ <i>H.annuus</i> +c	41±1.16bc
Soil +PAH+ <i>H.annuus</i> +p	49±1.16cde
Soil +PAH+ <i>H.annuus</i> +c/p	48±1.16bcd
Soil +PAH+300mg/kg Pb	31±0.6de
Soil +PAH+300mg/kg Pb + <i>H.annuus</i>	39±1.73e
Soil +PAH+300mg/kg Pb + <i>H.annuus</i> +c	44±0.6ef
Soil +PAH+300mg/kgPb + <i>H.annuus</i> +p	53±1.16f
Soil +PAH+300mg/kgPb + <i>H.annuus</i> +c/p	57±1.73f

Different letters indicate significant difference (TukeyHSD, $p \leq 0.05$). n=3, c=citric acid, p=potash, c/p=citric acid+potash, PAH=300mg/kg anthracene

Effect of citric acid, potash and citric acid+ potash on growth of Heianthus annuus L.

Given that natural low molecular weight organic acids (NLMWOA), such as citric acid, possess the capability to bind and detoxify intracellular heavy metals according to Luo *et al.* (2005), it is likely that the concentration of citric acid administered to the contaminated soil was adequate to mitigate the intracellular lead, thereby constraining the inhibition of plant growth. The inclusion of citric acids (CAs) could enhance the mobility and accessibility of lead, as suggested by Farid *et al.* (2020) This mechanism facilitated direct contact between the CAs-Pb chelate and plant roots, potentially leading to the uptake of lead-organic compounds by plants. This uptake might disrupt organelle metabolism processes, ultimately compromising cell membrane integrity and weakening photosynthesis. (Ranieri *et al.*, 2020). Conversely, according to Wang *et al.* (2016) and Xu *et al.* (2020), an over abundance of chelating agents could potentially strip divalent cations from the plasma membrane. This action may compromise the physiological integrity of root systems, causing irreversible damage and detrimental effects on plant growth. (Attinti *et al.*, 2017)

do Nascimento *et al.* (2006) noted that the presence of citric acid did not lead to any substantial variance in the dry matter yield

of *B. juncea*. Similarly, Luo *et al.* (2005) found that treating *Z. mays* and white beans with citric acid at a concentration of 5mmol/kg did not produce any significant effects on biomass. Increased pH levels following the application of potash can induce the precipitation of heavy metals in the soil. This process may subsequently diminish the mobility of heavy metals, thereby altering their redox state. Please in 2.0 (Materials and method, the initial ph level of the soil was established.)pH 4.8 This mechanism of heavy metal reduction and immobilization enhanced the biomass yield of *Heianthus annuus L* when potash was used as amendment. In anthracene-contaminated soil, the application of citric acid led to a minor reduction in the shoot dry matter of *Heianthus annuus L*. This decline could be attributed to the toxic influence exerted by the anthracene-contaminated soil on the growth of *Heianthus annuus L*. Additionally, it's plausible that the concentrations of amendments applied were insufficient to induce a more pronounced toxicity effect on *Heianthus annuus L*. than that caused by anthracene contamination alone. Furthermore, the combination of citric acid and potash resulted in a non-significant decrease in the shoot dry matter of *Heianthus annuus L*. (Figure 1). Conversely, in the presence of concurrent contamination with lead and anthracene, the combination

of citric acid and potash facilitated the growth of *Heianthus annuus L.* A notable ($p \leq 0.05$) rise in shoot dry matter was observed, suggesting that the current concentration of citric acid + potash could mitigate the growth inhibition induced by the co-contamination of anthracene and lead. Gunawardana *et al.* (2011) noted a significant increase in biomass yield of *L. perenne* with sulphate and citric acid treatments, albeit accompanied by enhanced accumulation of Cu. Similarly, Chigbo and Batty (2015) observed a heightened biomass yield of *Z. mays* when soil was amended with EDTA and citric acid. Consequently, plants treated with amendments that exert lower phytotoxicity and support high biomass production may be more effective in removing Pb from soil.

Effects of potash, citric acid and citric acid+potash on anthracene removal from soil

Table 2 illustrates the role of amendments in the removal of anthracene from soil in the current study. It is evident that in both single and co-contaminated soils, all tested amendments led to a significant increase in anthracene dissipation. Notably, potash + citric acid exhibited a more pronounced effect compared to citric acid and potash alone in co-contaminated soil, whereas in singly Pb-contaminated soil, potash demonstrated a more significant impact. By the end of the plant trial, the dissipation rates of anthracene with the application of citric acid, potash, and citric acid + potash reached 41%,

49%, and 48%, respectively (see Table 2). This suggests that citric acid + potash may have provided additional nutrients to indigenous microbes, fostering their proliferation and enhancing the biodegradation rate of anthracene in the soil.

This may be attributed to the rich concentration of nutrients like phosphate, nitrate and the metal potassium in potash. The presence of these nutrients may have enhanced the degradation ability of the microorganisms in the soil such that they were able to attack the polycyclic rings of the hydrocarbons thus being able to completely utilize them as their source of energy (Anikweet *al.*, 2017). Another possible explanation is that when the roots of *Heianthus annuus L.* release organic compounds, they may indirectly affect the solubility of PAHs by influencing microbial activity in the soil. It is conceivable that co-metabolism of citric acid and potash with anthracene occurred, thereby enhancing the biodegradation of anthracene, as suggested by Wei *et al.* (2009).

Conclusion

The current investigation examined the impact of citric acid and potash on the dry weight of *Heianthus annuus L.* in the remediation of co-contaminated soil. The findings revealed that in soil co-contaminated with Pb and anthracene, the combined application of potash + citric acid and potash stimulated the growth and dry weight of *Heianthus annuus L.*, resulting in an increase in biomass in both shoots and

roots. Conversely, the sole application of citric acid led to a 6% reduction in shoot dry matter yield for *Heianthus annuus L.* Additionally, a notable difference was observed in the shoot dry weights of plants grown in Pb and Pb-anthracene co-contaminated soil. Overall, the study demonstrates that the combined application of potash + citric acid and potash effectively promotes the growth and dry weight of *Heianthus annuus L.*, suggesting its potential applicability in remediating co-contaminated soils. (Yes, there is relationship between the growth of plant and its phytoemediation ability. High biomass plants accumulate more metals.) We only looked at the effect of these amendments on plant growth. The accumulation and translocation can still be another topic to look on.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank TETFUND for sponsoring this project through Institution Based Research (IBR).

Reference

- Afshan, S., Ali, S., Bharwana, S.A., Rizwan, M., Farid, M., Abbas, F., Ibrahim, M., Mehmood, M.A., Abbasi, G.H. (2015). Citric acid enhances the phytoextraction of chromium; plant growth; and photosynthesis by alleviating the oxidative damages in *Brassica napus L.* *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 22:11679–11689.
- Anikwe, M. A. N., Ikenganyia, E. E., Egbonimale, J., and Oputah, C. (2017). Assessment of some Tropical Plants for use in the Phytoremediation of Petroleum Contaminated oil: Effects of Remediation on Soil Physical and Chemical Properties. *International Journal of Plant & Soil Science*. 14, 2, 1-9.
- Ash, C., Tejnecký, V., Boruvka, L., Drabek, O. (2016). Different low-molecular-mass organic acids specifically control leaching of arsenic and lead from contaminated soil. *J. Contam. Hydrol.* 187:18–30.
- Attinti, R., Barrett, K.R., Datta, R., Sarkar, D. (2017). Ethylenediaminedisuccinic acid (EDDS) enhances phytoextraction of lead by vetiver grass from contaminated residential soils in a panel study in the field. *Environ. Pollut.* 225:524–533.
- Blaylock, M.J., Salt, D.E., Dushenkov, S., Zakharova, O., Gussman, C., Kapulnik, Y. (1997). Enhanced accumulation of Pb in Indian mustard by soil-applied chelating agents. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 31:860–865.
- Chigbo, C., and Batty, L. (2015). Chelate-Assisted Phytoremediation of Cu-Pyrene-Contaminated Soil Using *Z. mays*. *Water Air and Soil Pollution* 226,3,1-10.
- Chigbo, C., Batty, L., Bartlett, R. (2013). Interactions of copper and pyrene on phytoremediation potential of *Brassica juncea* in copper-pyrene co-contaminated soil. *Chemosphere*, 90, 2542-2548.
- do Nascimento, C.W.A., Amarasiriwardena, D., and Xing, B. (2006). Comparison of natural organic

- acids and synthetic chelates at enhancing phytoextraction of metals from a multi-metal contaminated soil. *Environmental Pollution*, 140, 114-123.
- Farid, M., Farid, S., Zubair, M., Rizwan, M., Ishaq, H.K., Ali, S., Ashraf, U., Alhaithloul, H.A.S., Gowayed, S., Soliman, M.H. (2020). Efficacy of *Zea mays* L. for the management of marble effluent contaminated soil under citric acid amendment; morpho-physiological and biochemical response. *Chemosphere*. 240:124930.
- Gunawardana, B., Singhal, N., and Johnson, A. (2011). Effects of amendments on copper, cadmium and lead phytoextraction by *lolium perenne* from multiple-metal contaminated solution. *International Journal of Phytoremediation* 13, 215-232.
- Guo, D., Ali, A., Ren, C., Du, J., Li, R., Lahori, A.H., Xiao, R., Zhang, Z.Y., Zhang, Z.Q. (2019). EDTA and organic acids assisted phytoextraction of Cd and Zn from a smelter contaminated soil by potherb mustard (*Brassica juncea*; Coss) and evaluation of its bioindicators. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 167:396–403.
- Han, Y., Zhang, L., Gu, J., Zhao, J., Fu, J. (2018). Citric acid and EDTA on the growth; photosynthetic properties and heavy metal accumulation of *Iris halophila* Pall. cultivated in Pb mine tailings. *Int. Biodeter. Biodeger.* 128:15–21.
- Hechmi, N., Aissa, N. B., Abdennaceur, H., and Jedidi, N. (2013). Phytoremediation Potential of maize (*Zea mays* L.) in co-contaminated soils with pentachlorophenol and cadmium. *Int. J. Phytorem.*, 15, 7,703-713.
- Khalid, A., Farid, M., Zubair, M., Rizwan, M., Iftikhar, U., Ishaq, H.K., Farid, S., Latif, U., Hina, K., Ali, S. (2020). Efficacy of *Alternanthera bettzickiana* to remediate copper and cobalt contaminated soil physiological and biochemical alterations. *Int. J. Environ. Res.*; 14:243–255.
- Luo, C., Shen, Z., and Li, X. (2005). Enhanced phytoextraction of Cu, Pb, Zn and Cd with EDTA and EDDS. *Chemosphere*, 59, 1-11.
- Najeeb, U., Jilani, G., Ali, S., Sarwar, M., Xu, L., Zhou, W. (2011). Insights into cadmium induced physiological and ultra-structural disorders in *Juncus effusus* L. and its remediation through exogenous citric acid. *J. Hazard Mater.* 186:565–574.
- Niu, Z., Li, X., Mahamood, M. (2023). Accumulation Potential Cadmium and Lead by Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) under Citric and Glutaric Acid-Assisted Phytoextraction. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 20, 5, 4107-415.
- Nwosu, O.U. (2023). Phytoremediation Potential of *Glycine max* L and Empty Palm Fruit Bunch Ash (Potash) in soils co-contaminated with Chromium and Anthracene. *Int. J. Adv. Sci. Eng.* 9, 4 3115-3120
- Ogbuehi H.C. (2016). Potential of Palm Bunch Ash Application on the Growth and Yield of Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.). *G.J.B.A.H.S.* 5.1:12-19.
- Piracha, M.A., Ashraf, M., Niaz, A. (2019). Arsenic fractionation and its impact

- on physiological behavior of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) in three texturally different soils under alkaline calcareous conditions. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 26:17438–17449.
- Ranieri, E., Moustakas, K., Barbaferi, M., Ranieri, A.C., Herrera-Melian, J.A., Petrella, A., Tommasi, F. (2020). Phytoextraction technologies for mercury- and chromium-contaminated soil: A review. *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 95:317–327.
- Sallah-Ud-Din, R., Farid, M., Saeed, R., Ali, S., Rizwan, M., Tauqeer, H.M., Bukhari, S.A.H. (2017). Citric acid enhanced the antioxidant defense system and chromium uptake by *Lemna minor* L. grown in hydroponics under Cr stress. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 24:17669–17678.
- Udoetok I. A. (2012). Characterization of ash made from oil palm empty fruit bunches (oefb). *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 3, 1.1-6.
- Wang, G., Zhang, S., Xu, X., Zhong, Q., Zhang, C., Jia, Y., Li, T., Deng, O., Li, Y. (2016). Heavy metal removal by GLDA washing: Optimization; redistribution; recycling; and changes in soil fertility. *Sci. Total Environ.* 11:557–568.
- Wei, X., Sang, L., Chen, J., Zhu, Y., and Zhang, Y. (2009). The effects of LMWOAs on biodegradation of multicomponent PAHs in aqueous solution using dual-wavelength fluorimetry. *Environmental pollution*, 157, 3150-3157.
- Xu, X., Chen, Q., Mo, S., Qian, Y., Wu, X., Jin, Y., Ding, H. (2020). Transcriptome-wide modulation combined with morpho-physiological analyses of *Typha orientalis* roots in response to lead challenge. *J. Hazard Mater.* 384:121405.